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ACPI Statement: Rediscovering the Healthy Scientific Temper

The Association of Christian Philosophers of India (ACPI) held its 44th annual research seminar at the St. Joseph Vaz Spiritual Renewal Centre, Old Goa, from 23rd to 25th October, 2019. The theme of the seminar was “Philosophizing Science: Promises, Perils and Possibilities”.

The Chief Guest at the inaugural function was Goa Archbishop Felipe Neri Ferrao. In his inaugural address, the Archbishop stressed the need for philosophy, science and faith to work productively together to create a better world.

The Keynote Address was prepared by Prof. Job Kozhamthadam, SJ, Director of the Indian Institute of Science and Religion, Delhi (IISR), which co-hosted the seminar. His paper was titled, “Science and Philosophy: Companions on a Common Mission”. He stressed the complementary nature of philosophy and science, and pointed out how these two disciplines independently and collaboratively had contributed towards the cumulative wisdom and development of the human family.

The papers presented pointed towards beneficial as well as dysfunctional aspects of various features and disciplines of science. The aspect of “promises” and “possibilities” of science and technology focused on the several accomplishments which the discipline of science has gifted the human family over the centuries. Many of these creative contributions
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